

**Innovative approaches to investigate the pathogenicity and genetics
of *Candida albicans*"**

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Tools to Study *Candida albicans* Pathogenicity and Genetics

Pathogenicity Assays

To measure *Candida albicans* virulence, various pathogenicity assays have been developed in recent years. These pathogenicity assays can be divided into **in vitro** assays and **in vivo** infection models.

In Vitro Assays

In vitro assays have been developed to assess the immune responses of various immune cell types such as monocytes (Mora-Montes et al., 2011), macrophages (Mora-Montes et al., 2012), neutrophils (Sheth et al., 2011), and dendritic cells (Hobson et al., 2004; Cambi et al., 2008). Such assays were deployed in this work. Assays also exist for measurement of phagocytosis (McKenzie et al., 2010; Bain et al., 2012; Lewis et al., 2012) and cytokine production (Mora-Montes et al., 2011; Mora-Montes et al., 2012). The measurement of pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory cytokines secreted when incubated with cells of *Candida* sp. are often assayed by Enzyme Linked Immune-Sorbent Assays (ELISA), radio-immuno assays (RIA), or Cytometric Bead Arrays (CBA). These assays have been used widely to assess the changes in immunological properties occurring in the cell wall of *C. albicans* mutants (Cheng et al., 2011; Netea et al., 2006). Other methods used to

study interactions between *Candida* and phagocytes have employed live cell imaging, video microscopy, and fluorescence-activated cell sorting (FACS) (McKenzie et al., 2010; Sheth et al., 2011). Other virulence, adhesion, and immune assays have also been developed using a range of cell lines and tissues, including reconstituted human epithelia and endothelia (Schaller et al., 2006).

In Vivo Models

Various in vivo models, including invertebrate models as mini-hosts and mouse models, have been developed for *Candida*. The invertebrate nematode *Caenorhabditis elegans* has been used to study virulence and antifungal drug screening in which *Candida* cells are introduced to the nematode by mixing them in their food (Anastassopoulou et al., 2011). The larval wax moth mini-host uses *Galleria mellonella*, in which the fungus is introduced by microinjection via pro-leg (Fuchs et al., 2010). The larval stage of the silk worm, *Bombyx mori*, can be inoculated with *Candida* via the thorax (Hanaoka et al., 2008), and the fruit fly, *Drosophila melanogaster*, has also been useful as a surrogate model for virulence, particularly when large numbers of animals need to be screened (Glittenberg et al., 2011). Despite the obvious differences in the immune systems of mammals and invertebrates, the rank order of relative virulence of a range of clinical *C. albicans* strains in mice was accurately recapitulated when the same strains were tested in *D. melanogaster* (Glittenberg et al., 2011). A vertebrate mini-host model, zebrafish (*Danio rerio*), which has both innate and adaptive immune systems, has also been used in recent years. In this model, *Candida* cells are normally injected into a seven-month-old zebrafish (Chao et al., 2010). These models have been developed to measure *Candida* virulence, host response to infectious agents, and the efficacy of antifungal drugs. Each model has its own

advantages and disadvantages, but the use of model systems has certainly diversified in recent years and proven to have utility in a wide range of contexts (MacCallum, 2012). Systemic mouse models are classically used to assess the virulence of *Candida* species, in which yeast cells are injected intravenously via the tail vein, and mouse mortality is analyzed usually over two to four weeks (Szabo and MacCallum, 2011). In mouse models, the assessment of loss of body weight can be used as an indicator of disease progression, while fungal organ burdens in the kidney—which is one of the main target organs—can be used to define the extent of disease progression. To understand the host response to fungal infection, in vivo cytokine levels can also be measured (Walker et al., 2009; Castillo et al., 2011). A similar infection model in rabbits has been particularly useful where large numbers of in vivo-grown fungal cells are required, e.g., for transcript profiling (Walker et al., 2009). Some short-term mouse intravenous models have recently been used where animals are terminated after only three days; estimation of virulence is determined based on loss of weight and fungal burden in the kidney (Walker et al., 2009; MacCallum, 2012). By using these shorter-term assays, suffering to animals can be reduced while still providing valuable information on infected tissue burdens and early host responses. To understand gut and vaginal infections caused by *Candida* sp., other mouse models—i.e., *Candida* gut colonization and dissemination infection models—have also been developed (Szabo and MacCallum, 2011).

Genetic Tools

A fundamental approach to connecting gene function with gene sequence has been to examine the phenotype of isogenic strains that have been constructed so that specific individual genes are deleted. One major method of gene disruption in *C.*

albicans has been the so-called ura-blaster method originally developed by Nancy Kleckner for constructing null mutants in diploid strains of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (Fonzi and Irwin, 1993). In this method, the URA3 gene is used as a recycled selectable marker for gene deletion. The ura-blaster disruption cassette uses direct repeat sequences of hisG that flank URA3. These provide a locus for cis recombination using the anti-metabolite 5-fluoro-orotic acid to screen for deletants that have lost URA3. URA3 can then be reused to delete the second copy of the gene. In 2004, it was recognized that this method generates null mutants that are heterozygous for URA3; single copies can still generate levels of gene product that become rate-limiting for growth during in vivo conditions (Brand et al., 2004). Thus, these null mutants can be partially auxotrophic for synthesis of uridine during in vivo virulence assays. To overcome this uridine autotrophy, this marker is now commonly inserted into the RPS1 locus, which gives relatively high levels of expression—presumed to be due to a relatively open heterochromatin structure at this locus (Brand et al., 2004). In addition, new markers such as LEU2, HIS1, and ARG4 have been developed that do not attenuate virulence when expressed in single copy. Cre-lox recombinase systems and SAT1-nourseothricin flipper systems are alternative gene disruption methods that are not based on nutritional auxotrophy (Dennison et al., 2005; Noble and Johnson, 2005; Samaranayake and Hanes, 2011). Recently developed shuttle vectors for integration at the NEUT5 locus have been claimed to provide native levels of expression (Gerami Nejad et al., 2013). To examine phenotypes associated with important essential genes, regulatable promoters have been developed to control expression levels. The most common promoters include ADH1, ACT1, TEF3, EF1- α 2, GAL1, PCK1, SAP2, MRP1, HEX1, MET3, MAL2, TET, and SAT1 (Nakayama et al., 2000; Reuss et al., 2004; Hanaoka et al., 2008; Gerami-

Nejad et al., 2009). Complementing studies on single gene disruptions, recent studies have generated mutants aimed at exploring genome-wide functional phenotypes. For example, a wide range of fluorescent markers have been developed—including GFP, YFP, CFP, RFP, mCherry, and Venus—which have been used to study protein localization and translational regulation (Keppler-Ross et al., 2008; Gerami-Nejad et al., 2009). With recent developments in genomic technology and availability of genomes from a wide range of pathogens, new methodologies in bioinformatics and systems biology analyses of *Candida* species have emerged (Arnaud et al., 2007). This version maintains scientific accuracy while using italics for all relevant scientific names.

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